

DNA extraction, amplification and sequencing for macrofungi (Basidiomycetes)

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The following protocols are commonly used for research at “Grupo de Pesquisa Cogumelos da Amazônia” (Research group in Amazonian Mushrooms), at Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazônia (National Institute of Amazonian Research) in collaboration with the Universidade Federal do Amazonas (Federal University of Amazonas), located in Manaus, Amazonas, Brazil.

DNA Extraction using CTAB (Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide)

This protocol is a standard protocol and adapted from Rogers & Bendich (1994) and Romano & Brasileiro (1999).

1. Cut a fragment of the mushroom or mycelial mass approximately 1cm x 1cm, and then further cut it into smaller pieces.
2. Transfer the fragments to a 1.5 ml polypropylene tube containing 500 µl of CTAB buffer preheated to 65°C and 3 zirconia beads (use metal beads if the material is harder). Close the tube and mix gently. For complete maceration, homogenize in the Precellys 24 Lysis & Homogenization system at 5000 rpm for 3 cycles of 40 seconds with intervals of 5 seconds between each cycle.
3. Incubate the samples in a water bath (or dry bath) at 60°C for 30 minutes, occasionally shaking the tube to keep the extract suspended.
4. Remove the tube from the water bath and allow the mixture to reach room temperature. Add 500 µl of chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (24:1; v/v). Close the tube and manually mix for 10 minutes.
5. Centrifuge at 5,000 g for 10 minutes at room temperature to separate the organic phase from the aqueous phase.
6. Remove the aqueous phase (upper phase) to a new 1.5 ml tube. Avoid collecting any denatured proteins present at the interface.

7. Repeat the extraction with chloroform:isoamyl alcohol one or two more times (steps 4 to 6), considering that additional extractions may result in a purer sample but with potential higher DNA losses.
8. Add 0.6 volumes of isopropanol or 2.5 volumes of absolute ethanol, both at -20°C . Mix gently until a precipitate forms.
9. The DNA-CTAB complex obtained may form a visible filamentous network or not. Recover the DNA by centrifuging the sample at 10,000 g for 20 minutes. In a successful preparation, the DNA should not appear dark.
10. Discard the supernatant and wash the precipitate with $\sim 300\ \mu\text{l}$ of 70% ethanol (v/v). If the precipitate becomes loose during washing, repeat the centrifugation step for 3 minutes (step 9).
11. Discard the supernatant and air-dry the precipitate by inverting the tube on a paper towel. Alternatively, the material can be dried at 37°C in a thermal cycler until the liquid is completely removed.
12. Dissolve the precipitate in $50\ \mu\text{l}$ of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0; 1 mM EDTA) or ultrapure water and incubate at 4°C for half an hour or longer. The sample can then be stored at -20°C .

***CTAB extraction Buffer**

For 100 mL:

- CTAB – 2 g
- NaCl 1.4M – 28 mL (from a 5 M solution)
- Tris-HCl 100mM pH 8 – 10mL (from a 1 M solution)
- EDTA 20mM – 4 mL (from a 0.5 M solution)
- Distilled water up to 100mL

Dissolve all reagents, leaving CTAB for last. Keep stirring while heating. Sterilize by autoclaving.

Alternative protocols

DNA extraction kits are also used (e.g. DNeasy Plant Kit – Qiagen). DNA can be also extracted from stored samples on QIAcard FTA PlantSaver, following manufacture's protocols. These protocols yield DNA of higher quality but in lower quantities. Therefore, the choice of the method depends on both the material to be analyzed and the availability of financial resources.

DNA amplification

The commonly used DNA regions in molecular phylogeny studies include the ribosomal regions nrITS (ITS1 + 5.8S + ITS2), nucLSU (28S), as well as the nuclear regions elongation factor 1-alpha (TEF-1 α), rpb2 (DNA-directed RNA polymerase II core subunit 2), rpb1 (DNA-directed RNA polymerase II subunit 1), and ATP6 (mitochondrial ATPase subunit 6). We follow cycling conditions available at Rehner & Buckley (2005), Kretzer & Bruns (1999), Matheny (2005) and White et al. (1990). Some adaptations are needed depending on the *taxa* being studied.

PCR mix

We commonly use the KAPA Taq PCR Kit with a final reaction volume of 25 μ l, refer to Table 1 for the reaction conditions.

Table 1. PCR Reaction Example for 41 samples using a pair of nrITS primers. It is recommended to prepare the mix for the number of samples + 2 to avoid pipetting errors. The quantities to be used for the mix are indicated in green.

PCR Reaction	Mix for 43 samples
PCR Buffer + MgCl ₂ - 2 μ l	43 * 2 μ l = 86 μl
dNTP (10 mM each) – 0.5 μ l	43 * 0.5 μ l = 21.5 μl
Primer ITS (Forward) – 0.5 μ l	43 * 0.5 μ l = 21.5 μl
Primer ITS (Reverse) – 0.5 μ l	43 * 0.5 μ l = 21.5 μl
DNA – 1 to 6 μ l	-
Taq DNA polymerase – 0.08 μ l	43 * 0.08 μ l = 3.44 μl
H ₂ O – 15.42 μ l	43 * 15.42 μ l = 663.06 μl

Total: 25 µl	
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After preparing the mix, dispense 19 µl of the mix into each tube (or well) and add 1 to 6 µl of the DNA solution (depending on the DNA concentration).

After completing the PCR, 5µl of the sample is mixed with 5µl of running buffer (glycerol and bromophenol blue and GelRed), deposited onto a 1.5% agarose gel, and visualized under ultraviolet light.

Purification of PCR Fragments

For the purification of amplified sequences, the ExoSAP-IT™ enzyme kit was used. To do this, 2 µl of ExoSAP-IT™ and 5 µl of each sample are added to a 200 µl polypropylene tube, and then subjected to a thermal cycler, following the manufacturer's recommendations (37°C for 15 minutes, followed by 15 minutes at 80°C).

DNA sequencing

The sequencing of PCR fragments is carried out using sequencing kits from Applied Biosystems ABI PRISM® BigDye™ Terminator Cycle Sequencing Ready Reaction Kit version 3.1. The primers used for sequencing are typically the same as those used for amplification. For sequencing, a mix was prepared with the reagents and proportions shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Example of Sequencing Reaction for 24 samples using a pair of nrITS primers. It is recommended to prepare the mix for the number of samples + 2 to avoid pipetting errors. The quantities to be used for the mix are indicated in green.

Sequencing Reaction	Mix for 26 samples (ITS – Forward)	Mix for 26 samples (ITS – Reverse)
Ultrapure H ₂ O – 4.5 µl	26 * 4.5 µl = 117 µl	26 * 4.5 µl = 117 µl
DNA (Purified PCR solution) – 2 µl	-	-
BigDye – 0.5 µl	26 * 0.5 µl = 13 µl	26 * 0.5 µl = 13 µl
BigDye Buffer – 2 µl	26 * 2 µl = 52 µl	26 * 2 µl = 52 µl
Primer (5 mM) – 1µl	26 µl	26 µl

Total: 10 μ l		
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After preparing the mix, dispense 8 μ l into each well of the plate, add 2 μ l of the purified PCR solution, and place it in the thermal cycler following the program below:

Initial denaturation	Cycling	Hold
80°C - 5min	30x 96°C – 10 sec; 50°C – 5 sec; 60°C – 4min	10°C

DNA precipitation using NG solution

The DNA precipitation is performed using the protocol with NG solution (glycogen to final concentration of 1 μ g/ μ l, and 3M sodium acetate), following the steps below:

1. Add 6 μ l of NG solution to the sequencing plate and vortex to mix.
2. Add 45 μ l of 100% ethanol and vortex.
3. Incubate at -20°C for 30 minutes.
4. Centrifuge at 2000 RCF (maximum speed) for 45 minutes, with the plate facing up.
5. Centrifuge at 200 RCF with the plate inverted for 30 seconds.
6. Add 110 μ l of 70% Ethanol and vortex.
7. Centrifuge for 15 minutes at maximum speed, with the plate facing up.
8. Centrifuge at 200 RCF with the plate inverted for 30 seconds.
9. Add 110 μ l of 70% Ethanol and vortex.
10. Centrifuge for 5 minutes at maximum speed, with the plate facing up.
11. Centrifuge at 200 RCF with the plate inverted for 30 seconds.
12. Dry the plate for 5 minutes at 52°C (use a thermal cycler).
13. Add 10 μ l of Hi-Di Formamide and vortex, and it is ready to be sequenced.

References

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